

THE ESSENCE OF THE AUTOPLANTATION METHOD AND THE IMPROVEMENT OF THE DIAGNOSTIC-TREATMENT ALGORITHM OF DIFFUSE TOXIC BULLOCKS

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Relevance and necessity of the topic. A distinctive feature of the transplantation of endocrine structures is the ability to transplant them in the form of an entire organ, its fragment and even individual cells, which opens up surgically easily accessible, free transplant Pathways [2;5]. Transplant methods differ mainly in the place of introduction of thyroid tissue culture [3;6]. The most effective transplant zone is not fully studied [5]. Th transplantation was performed using autoallo and xenotransplantates. Experimental research on Th auto transplantation has been ongoing for over 100 years [4;5]. There has been an increased interest in thyroid tissue transplantation for those with hypothyroidism. At the same time, the postoperative mortality rate remains high, the cost of internship intervention is very high, long-term immunosuppressive therapy is necessary, complications of immunosuppressive and surgical nature reach 75% [1;2;7].

Thus, cell transplantation has proven its consistency, certain achievements of endocrine cell transplantation and increased interest of clinicians in this problem should contribute to significant progress in the treatment of endocrine tyropathies.

The purpose of scientific research. The essence of the auto plantation method and the improvement of the diagnostic-treatment algorithm of diffuse toxic throat.

Andijan State Medical Institute Y. Otabekov's Department of surgery III also featured the medical history, operational journal data, and associated outpatient cards of 263 patients who underwent diffuse toxic throat (DTB) surgery from 2010 to 2019. A retrospective assessment of 263 patients who had been treated and left showed that 120 had been St tasrikhi performed, from which: 76 were found to leave up to 1.0 gr in the thyroid seat, 30 to 1.1+2.0 gr, and 14 to 2.1+3.0 gr. Patients who underwent this ST surgery became known as Group 1.

In 65 patients after 1.263 patients, an additional cut-off 1,0-gram gland autotransplantate was planted over the subtotal thyroidectomy tasrix. These were left in 41 of the 1.0 gr. on the gland +1,0 + 2,0 gr. autotransplantat, 1.1+2.0 gr left in 13 persons. on the gland +1,0 + 2,0 gr. autotransplantat, 2.1+3.0 gr left in 11 persons. on the gland +1,0 + 2,0 gr. autotransplantat is planted with glandular tissue. We have designated patients with this subtotal thyroidectomy + performed as Group 2.

In 78 patients after 263 patients, total thyroidectomy was isolated from under the gland by attaching a silky thread knot with an uninterrupted connection in addition to the tasrix, but not separated from the glandular base. That is, up to +1.0 gr over the node (n=51), up to 1.1+2.0 gr (n=15), up to 2.1+3.0 gr (N=12) left the patient untouched in the glandular seat without extension. Total thyroidectomy was referred to as glandular Autoplant leaving Group 3 (TTAP) in conjunction with the transfer.

Between 2010 and 2019, when we divided 263 patients who had diffuse toxic throat surgery into women and men: 228 (86.7%) were women and 35 (13.3%) were men and 7:1 ratio when women were men. Enlargement of the thyroid gland at Level II-19 (7.2%) individuals, enlargement at Level III – 124 (47.1%) individuals, enlargement at Level IV-92 (35%) individuals, and Enlargement at Level V – 28 (10.6%) patients. It was noted from the table that the largest number of patients applied with an increase in Level III and Level IV.

Research methods.

The complaints and medical history of the 263 patients who applied were thoroughly studied, the following examination methods were used.

Clinical objective and subjective examinations were carried out in 263 patients (examination, palpation).

Instrumental examinations: ultrasound examination (UTT) and electrocardio-gram (ECG) were used in 263 patients.

Biochemical analyzes: an examination of serum "cholesterol" levels was carried out in 242 patients. Total serum calcium(Ca+) levels as well as those in the forehead were tested in 263 patients and phosphorus(r+) levels were tested in 12 patients.

Radioimmunological tests: T3, T4, TTG, anti-TPO, anti-TGS were tested in 225 patients, paratgormoni-in 3 patients.

Contrast computed tomography: performed in 36 patients with the aim of examining the cervical, spinal, spinal and thoracic Sox.

58 patients with thin needle puncture biopsy (IIPB) were examined in an

outpatient manner.

Postoperative hysto-pathomorphological testing was performed in 263 patients.

Statistical analysis. The results from the checks were used in the calculation of the "Excel" program and reliable differences in the WINDOWS_XP environment, the T - criterion of the Styudent. The comparative difference between the groups was checked by the magnitude of the Styudent criterion p-E-0.05, p-e-0.01, p-e-0.001.

Results and references. The essence of the autoplantation method. The concept of an Autoplant is to leave an untouched non-elongate Autoplant in the glandular seat in the hole, which separates the thyroid tissue from its location by a nodular suture. Out of the 78 patients who performed Total thyreoidectomy, 51 were left with an autoplant of +1.0 gr over the node. 15 were left with an autoplant between 1.1 gr and+2.0 gr over the node. 12 were left with 2.1 gr to + 3.0 gr of autoplant tissue over the node, and a total thyreoidectomy operation was performed with a cut over it. The fact that the gland itself was rich in blood vessels, while the tissue of the fascia was also rich in blood vessels, caused Shyevkunenko's fascia to be re-wrapped over the autoplant and sutured and fixated. In order to regenerate the Autoplant, a knot was formed beneath the thyroid gland itself and a bandage was formed over it by fascia. But remains stuck with the top side, which is attached to the fascia. Even if the Autoplant is isolated for a certain time, after fixation, soon (from 1 week to 6 months) collagen fibers in the fascia grow into the follicles-aro of the Autoplant together with blood vessels. Collagen fibers and blood vessels entering the Autoplant parenchyma capture the transplant. From under the gland Autoplant - over the trahea plates, fastsial collagen fibers are pinched with a nodular suture, so that the tissue between them is absorbed in 7-8 days. With an Autoplant, the trahea plate is isolated from one another. As a result, the autoplant from the base of the gland becomes lonely. During this period (1-6 months), the disconnected autoplant can also shrink to a certain part or be completely absorbed. A large amount of T3-T4 hormones, which are absorbed into the blood through the thyroid tissue, are synthesized during this period and destroyed at the end of the term, the amount of T3-T4 hormones in the blood is normalized or reduced. The fascia, where the upper surface of some areas of Autoplant tissue that have been left unabsorbed, is fused with the blood vessels, meaning that blood vessels grow into the autoplant parenchyma and activate the plantation. Applying laser light to plant tissue remaining on the surface of the trachea also leads to

reparative regeneration of the glandular tissue and plant. The development of the plantation can lead to recurrence of DTB in some cases, the development and duration of weight levels, and functional and morphometric changes in tissue. In the postoperative period, the absorbed and non-absorbed part of the Autoplant leads to regeneration and stimulation of its function. Thyreoid complements hormone deficiency. That is, failure is prevented by this reserve until the base of the thyroid gland completely compensates the body. Saturates the deficits with calcium elements. The Autoplant prevents itself from being stimulated by TTG.

Improvement of the diagnostic-treatment algorithm for diffuse toxic bull. And the methods of examination that we apply and offer, firstly, there are a lot of clinics, and in business activities, and secondly, to show the DTB every clinical signs, there are opportunities in the apparatus in which this is being applied. One is used even when applied from the device or is forgotten without application. Fourth, hyperdiagnostics or hypodiagnosics should not be allowed. From the fifth to the surgery, hypodiagnosics are performed and the surgery is followed by another diagnosis on a histo-morphological examination. An operation with this will not be advisable. From the sixth, TPO-antibodies, Tg-antibodies, TTG-antibodies were included in further investigations to this day, since these investigations were considered as predictors of complications. In addition to other Hech which complications of a disease are not as common as DTB disease. To avoid complications after the operation, TPO-antithela Tg-antithela was included among the main examinations, similar to hormonal examinations of TTG-antitheles. Seventh, the improved operation that we are staying with has led to a significant reduction in complications. For this reason, it was considered desirable to bring into the algorithm layout. The eighth consists of monitoring, taxing and monitoring the quality of the patient's life, of course, long-term results after long-term and ongoing operations. Hence, the diagnostic-treatment algorithm for diffuse toxic Bull: this-retrospective results were considered to increase the effectiveness of treatment under diagnostic improvement.

Conclusion. So, in the process of our scientific and practical work, we have improved the essence of the autoplantation method and the diagnostic-treatment algorithm for diffuse toxic Bull, which has led to an improvement in the results of treatment by sugary.

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